

The Apache Software Foundation (ASF) is researching the state of our community through this survey. It will prompt you to provide basic information on your contributor role, your experiences with, and perceptions of, the Apache community, as well as some demographic information. The ASF promotes open, community-focused projects that are welcoming to all.

Your survey responses will help us understand to what extent we are meeting our equality, diversity, and inclusion objectives. The survey is estimated to take approximately 15 minutes of your time and is voluntary. Data will be aggregated and anonymized to help us understand the experiences of different groups. Your responses will be anonymous and no IP addresses will be recorded.

See our Blog post or Wiki page for more information about this survey.

If you have further questions, please contact the administrators of this survey: Katia Rojas (katia@apache.org) or Anita Sarma (asarma@gmail.com).

Before starting two tips: (1) survey can be saved and continued later, and (2) do not use browser back button, but the "Previous" button at the end of the page.

For collected data, we are following the Apache Privacy Policy. By clicking "next", you acknowledge to participate voluntarily and to have read the text on this page.

Section A: Contributor Roles and Tenure

A1. How long have you been involved with the ASF?

Less than 1 year

1 to 2 years

3 to 5 years

6 to 10 years

Over 10 years

A2. Which of the following tasks did you start with when you got involved in the ASF? Select as many as are relevant.

Contributing/reviewing code

Creating or maintaining documentation

Translating documentation

	Less than a year	1-2 years	3-5 years	6-10 years	10+ years	Not Applicable
PMC	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Mentor	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Member	<input type="checkbox"/>					
VP/Chair	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Board	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Section B: Motivation

B1. On average, how much time per week are you available to work on OSS projects?

Paid hours

Unpaid hours

B2. If you get paid, who pays for your contributions?

- I don't get paid
- I get paid by my employer to contribute
- I am a freelancer and my customers pay for contributions as part of my contract
- I receive grants from independent organizations (foundations, research etc.)
- I get sponsored by stakeholders in the project I contribute to
- Other

Other

B3. If you would like to get paid more, what stops you from doing it?

- I don't want to be paid more
- I don't know how to find those who will pay for my time
- I don't know how to ask to be paid (either to my employer or customers)
- I have potential customers but I do not know how to manage the business relationship (contract/agreements/work orders)
- I have legal obstacles that prevent me from being paid (organizational policies/conflict of interests)

Other

Other

Section C: Availability of Protocols / Guidelines

C1. How often do you consult the following ASF policies, processes, or guidelines regarding...?

	Never	Rarely (less than once a month)	Sometimes (more than once a month)	Often (once a week or more)	Not Applicable
Mailing list communication	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
IRC communication	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Performing code reviews	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Process of getting code accepted	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Code of conduct	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Onboarding newcomers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Licensing, trademark	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Add new committers/PMC members	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Project releases	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Voting process	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Handling security vulnerabilities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

C2. When you need to locate information about ASF processes, policies, or guidelines, which of the following describes your experience?

	Always easy to find	Easy to find	A little difficult to find	Quite difficult to find	Not Applicable
Mailing list communication	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
IRC communication	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Performing code reviews	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Process of getting code accepted	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Always easy to find	Easy to find	A little difficult to find	Quite difficult to find	Not Applicable
Code of conduct	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Onboarding newcomers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Licensing, trademark	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Add new committers/PMC members	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Project releases	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Voting process	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Handling security vulnerabilities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section D: Support for Contributors

D1. Do you have a mentor(s) in the ASF?

Yes

No

I am looking for one

D2. Do you face challenges when participating in the ASF (e.g., language differences, technical expertise, cultural differences, etc)?

No challenges

A Few challenges

Several challenges

Many challenges

D3. How often do you face the following challenges when participating in the ASF?

	Never	Rarely (less than once a month)	Sometimes (more than once a month)	Often (once a week or more)
Process related challenges with getting started on the project	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Process related challenges with navigating the contribution process	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Process related challenges with reception issues in the project	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Process related challenges with licenses	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Social Challenges with communication styles	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Social Challenges with feeling imposter syndrome/ fear of making mistakes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Never	Rarely (less than once a month)	Sometimes (more than once a month)	Often (once a week or more)
Social Challenges with facing a lack of recognition	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Social Challenges with toxic/ unwelcoming environment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Social Challenges with located in a different country/from a different nationality	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Social Challenges with cultural differences	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Project related challenges with documentation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Project related challenges with technical Hurdles (e.g., environment setup, specific code characteristics)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section E: Diversity and Inclusion

E1. Thinking about your current project(s), please rate the following statements.

	Completely disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Completely agree
I feel that I belong to the project.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other members of the project see me as a parental figure.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am expected to take care of other members of the project more than is usual.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I have a hard time following discussions because of technical jargon.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I feel some members of the community are patronizing to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I have an equal chance to get contributions accepted.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Nothing keeps me from contributing to the project.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I have a solid network of open-source peers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
It was easy to find a mentor with whom I felt comfortable.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The PMC represents a diverse set of people.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I feel represented in the decision making group.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I was made aware of the code of conduct and how to report violations.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I felt safer and more empowered to fully participate in this project because it followed the code of conduct.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

E2. Please choose your country of residence.

Afghanistan

▼

- Albania
- Algeria
- American Samoa
- Andorra
- Angola
- Anguilla
- Antigua and Barbuda
- Argentina
- Armenia
- Aruba
- Australia
- Austria
- Azerbaijan
- Bahamas
- Bahrain
- Bangladesh
- Barbados
- Belarus
- Belgium
- Belize
- Benin
- Bermuda
- Bhutan
- Bolivia (Plurinational State of)
- Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Botswana
- Brazil
- British Virgin Islands

Brunei Darussalam	<input type="checkbox"/>
Bulgaria	<input type="checkbox"/>
Burkina Faso	<input type="checkbox"/>
Burundi	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cabo Verde	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cambodia	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cameroon	<input type="checkbox"/>
Canada	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cayman Islands	<input type="checkbox"/>
Central African Republic	<input type="checkbox"/>
Chad	<input type="checkbox"/>
Channel Islands	<input type="checkbox"/>
Chile	<input type="checkbox"/>
China	<input type="checkbox"/>
China, Hong Kong SAR	<input type="checkbox"/>
China, Macao SAR	<input type="checkbox"/>
Colombia	<input type="checkbox"/>
Comoros	<input type="checkbox"/>
Congo	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cook Islands	<input type="checkbox"/>
Costa Rica	<input type="checkbox"/>
Croatia	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cuba	<input type="checkbox"/>
Curaçao	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cyprus	<input type="checkbox"/>
Czechia	<input type="checkbox"/>
Côte d'Ivoire	<input type="checkbox"/>
Democratic People's Republic of Korea	<input type="checkbox"/>
Democratic Republic of the Congo	<input type="checkbox"/>

Denmark

Djibouti

Dominica

Dominican Republic

Ecuador

Egypt

El Salvador

Equatorial Guinea

Eritrea

Estonia

Eswatini

Ethiopia

Falkland Islands (Malvinas)

Faroe Islands

Fiji

Finland

France

French Guiana

French Polynesia

Gabon

Gambia

Georgia

Germany

Ghana

Gibraltar

Greece

Greenland

Grenada

Guadeloupe

- Guam
- Guatemala
- Guinea
- Guinea-Bissau
- Guyana
- Haiti
- Holy See
- Honduras
- Hungary
- Iceland
- India
- Indonesia
- Iran (Islamic Republic of)
- Iraq
- Ireland
- Isle of Man
- Israel
- Italy
- Jamaica
- Japan
- Jordan
- Kazakhstan
- Kenya
- Kiribati
- Kuwait
- Kyrgyzstan
- Lao People's Democratic Republic
- Latvia
- Lebanon

	Lesotho	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Liberia	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Libya	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Liechtenstein	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lithuania	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Luxembourg	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Madagascar	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Malawi	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Malaysia	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Maldives	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Mali	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Malta	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Marshall Islands	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Martinique	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Mauritania	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Mauritius	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Mayotte	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Mexico	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Micronesia (Federated States of)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Monaco	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Mongolia	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Montenegro	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Montserrat	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Morocco	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Mozambique	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Myanmar	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Namibia	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Nauru	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Nepal	<input type="checkbox"/>
		▼

Netherlands

New Caledonia

New Zealand

Nicaragua

Niger

Nigeria

Niue

Northern Mariana Islands

Norway

Oman

Pakistan

Palau

Panama

Papua New Guinea

Paraguay

Peru

Philippines

Poland

Portugal

Puerto Rico

Qatar

Republic of Korea

Republic of Moldova

Romania

Russian Federation

Rwanda

Réunion

Saint Helena

Saint Kitts and Nevis

- Saint Lucia
- Saint Pierre and Miquelon
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
- Samoa
- San Marino
- Sao Tome and Principe
- Saudi Arabia
- Senegal
- Serbia
- Seychelles
- Sierra Leone
- Singapore
- Sint Maarten (Dutch part)
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Solomon Islands
- Somalia
- South Africa
- South Sudan
- Spain
- Sri Lanka
- State of Palestine
- Sudan
- Suriname
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Syrian Arab Republic
- Tajikistan
- Thailand

The former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia

Timor-Leste

Togo

Tokelau

Tonga

Trinidad and Tobago

Tunisia

Turkey

Turkmenistan

Turks and Caicos Islands

Tuvalu

Uganda

Ukraine

United Arab Emirates

United Kingdom

United Republic of Tanzania

United States Virgin Islands

United States of America

Uruguay

Uzbekistan

Vanuatu

Venezuela (Bolivarian Republic of)

Viet Nam

Wallis and Futuna Islands

Western Sahara

Yemen

Zambia

Zimbabwe

E3. How confident are you in your ability to read, write and speak in English when performing the following activities?

	Uncomfortable	Not confident (can speak, but difficult)	Average	Confident	Very confident (fluent)
Performing reviews	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Participating in a non-technical discussion on the email list	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Participating in technical discussions on the email list	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Speaking with others (face to face)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

E4. What is your age range?

24 or younger

25 to 34

35 to 44

45 to 54

55 to 64

Over 65

E5. How do you identify yourself?

Woman

Man

Gender variant / Non-conforming / Non-binary

Prefer not to say

Prefer to self-describe (please answer as comment)

Prefer to self-describe (please answer as comment)

E6. What is your education level (or equivalent)?

- No formal education
- High school
- Technical training
- Undergraduate degree
- Master's degree
- Ph.D

E7. What parts of your life does your dis/ability affect?

- None , I don't have a dis/ability.
- My dis/ability affects focus, memory, and attention.
- My dis/ability affects my emotions and how I perceive the emotions of others.
- My dis/ability affects my hearing.
- My dis/ability affects my mood, thinking, and behavior.
- My dis/ability affects how I move.
- My dis/ability affects my vision.
- Prefer not to answer.
- My dis/ability affects another part of my life as follows:

My dis/ability affects another part of my life as follows:

Section F: Wrap Up

F1. What else do you think we should know about this survey or about EDI (Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion) in the ASF?